

New methods of chemical functionalization of peat

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Peat is a unique natural composite, a source of humic substances and raw materials for industry and agriculture. The aim of this work is to develop a new carboxymethyl derivatives from peat to study the possibility of its application in the industry oil and gas production [1]. The influence of duration mechanochemical treatment of peat on the process of carboxymethylation under the action of natrium monochloroacetic salt in the presence of NaOH, the temperature of the alkylation – 25 °C (tabl. 1) [2]. The influence of duration mechanochemical treatment of peat on the process of benzylation under the action of benzyl chloride in the presence of NaOH (tabl. 1) [2]. The chemical composition of products of benzylation of peat given in the table 2.

Table 1. The influence of the molar ratio of OH:NaOH:m-ClAcNa in the carboxymethylation of peat in conditions of intensive mechanical grinding on the properties of the obtained products

Sample	Duration carboxymethylation of peat, min	Content of carboxymethyl groups, %	Solubility in water, %
Peat	-	-	5
1	10	17.9	42
2	20	20.5	69
3	30	20.7	71
4	60	24.7	76

It was found that with an increase in the molar ratio there is an increase in the content of bound carboxymethyl groups in products and their solubility in water (tabl. 1).

Table 2. Benzylation of peat

Duration benzylation of peat, min	Content of benzyl groups, %	Solubility in chloroform, %
10	3.8	17
20	4.7	25
30	5.9	36
40	6.8	45
50	7.7	53
60	8.6	60

It is shown that the increase in the duration benzylation of peat is the increase in the content and solubility products in chloroform (tabl. 2).

References

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